

SPHERICAL TRIANGLE AND ITS BASIC FORMULAS. PARALACTIC TRIANGLE, COORDINATE SUBSTITUTION FORMULAS

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Abstract. *This article will illustrate the formulas for spherical triangle and its basis and explanation, as well.*

Keywords: *celestial sphere, point, straight line, circle, coordinate, ecliptic coordinate, Equatorial coordinate system, horizontal coordinate system.*

The coordinates of the luminaries in the celestial sphere are separated into the coordinate system shown below:

Let's consider the following basic coordinate systems that are most used in astronomy:

Horizontal coordinate system;

First Equatorial coordinate system;

• Second Equatorial coordinate system;

Ecliptic coordinate system;

Geographic coordinate system;

These said coordinate systems are a celestial spherical coordinate system, named in a manner consistent with the name of its larger circle.

The celestial sphere is said to be a hypothetical sphere with an arbitrary radius at the center of which the observer is standing. To this sphere we project the situations of the celestial luminaries.

Vertical line: a line passing through the center of the celestial sphere and parallel to the direction of the force of gravity.

Zenith (Z) and nadir points (Z/): points of the vertical line intersecting with the celestial sphere.

Mathematical horizon: a large circle perpendicular to the vertical line, consisting of a horizontal plane intersecting with the celestial sphere passing through the center of the celestial sphere.

Axis of the universe: a line that passes through the center of the celestial sphere and where the invisible daily movement of the celestial sphere occurs, that is, parallel to the axis of the Earth's rotation.

North (R) and South (r/) poles of the universe: points of intersection of the axis of the universe with the celestial sphere.

Celestial equator: a large circular plane perpendicular to the axis of the universe passing through the center of the celestial sphere and intersecting with the celestial sphere.

Celestial Meridian: a great circle passing through the pole of the universe and Zenith points.

Points north (N) and South (s): points where the horizon and meridian intersect. The North Point lies below the North Pole of the universe on the horizon.

Descent line (NS): a straight line that intersects the Horizon plane and the celestial Meridian.

Points East (E) and west (W): points of the equator intersecting with the horizon.

Points of the equator (Q, Q'): points of the equator intersecting with the meridian.

Vertical circles or verticals: large circles passing through the zenith point and perpendicular to the horizon.

First Vertical: a vertical circle perpendicular to the meridian plane passing through Points East (E) and west (W).

The angle of inclination of the axis of the universe to the horizon is equal to the geographical width of the place of observation (s) (theorem on the height of the pole of the universe from the horizon).

Ecliptic: a large circle of the sun's center that is visible for a year in relation to the stars (or constellations) on the celestial sphere.

Vernal (e.g.) and autumnal (e.g.) Equinox points: intersecting points of the ecliptic and Equator.

In the celestial sphere, the state of a point (specifically, the illuminator) is determined by 2 coordinates on the surface of the sphere. The most commonly used such coordinate system is four. In each of these, the position of the point is determined by two coordinates, one of which gives the angular distance of the point from any major circle plane, and the other is calculated starting from some specific point of it lying on this circle plane. Thus, one coordinate forms a large circular arc and the other coordinate a spherical angle.

The main circle of the horizontal coordinate system is the horizon circle. The geometric poles of the horizon are the zenith point Z and the nadir point Z' . PZP/ Z / - the celestial Meridian will be the starting circle, and the coordinate number Head will be the Southern Point S . The coordinates of this system are: beam height and beam azimuth. The height of the illuminator is understood to be the Yei $M\sigma$ of the Illuminator vertical $z\sigma z'$ from the horizon to the Illuminator. The height of the beam is denoted by the letter h - and is calculated from the horizon to Zenith from 0° to $+90^\circ$, and Nadir from 0° to -90° . In most cases, the height of the clamp is replaced by the zenith distance of the Illuminator. When explaining this horizontal coordinate to readers, we will use the following celestial sphere and indicate the height of the luminaire, the distance of the zenith.

The position of luminaires in the horizontal coordinate system is characterized by two coordinates.

One of these is called the azimuth of the highlighter a , the other its height H . In this system, the South Point is taken, making the coordinate head.

The azimuth of the illuminator is said to be the spherical angle of the diameter half a circle passed through the Illuminator, formed in Zenith by the diameter of the sky. Often the diameter is measured by an arc that is retracted at this angle and is oriented along a mathematical horizon, i.e. the arc length from the South s point to the S point where the diameter intersects the mathematical horizon of the semicircle. And the height of the luminaire is measured by the length of the arc from Point s to Point m – the diameter of which passed through the luminaire intersects with the mathematical horizon of the semicircle.

For an observer at the center of the celestial sphere, diameter A , measured in the direction of the clock arrow along the mathematical horizon, is positive-sign, and negative-sign in the

opposite direction. The measurement limit is $\pm 180^\circ$. Height h is a positive signal over a mathematical horizon, and below it is a negative signal. Instead of the height h of the highlighter, sometimes its distance from the zenith z is taken.

$$h + z = 90^\circ$$

given one of these sizes from the one, the other is easily found. The horizontal coordinate system magnitudes A and h (or z) are measured in Arc degrees, minutes, and seconds. The disadvantage of this coordinate system is that the horizontal coordinates of the Illuminator also change as the observer changes position in the globe. With this diameter you can take work only at certain Observatory or observation points diameter.

A triangle formed by the intersection of three large circles on a sphere is called a spherical triangle. A spherical triangle differs from a flat triangle in that the sum of its inner angles is greater than 180° and less than 540° . In a spherical triangle ABC , its sides (a, b, c) and spherical angles (A, B, C) are in the same bond as in the formulas below.

Basic formulas of spherical trigonometry:

1) cosine theorem: $\cos a = \cos b \cos c + \sin b \sin c \cos A$

2) sine theorem: $\frac{\sin a}{\sin A} = \frac{\sin b}{\sin B} = \frac{\sin c}{\sin C}$

3) Five-element formula:

$$\sin a \cos B = \sin c \cos b - \cos c \sin b \cos A$$

$a \rightarrow b \rightarrow c \rightarrow a \rightarrow \dots$, $A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C \rightarrow A \rightarrow \dots$ there is a substitution rule along. As a result, the above theorem formulas change in shape only.

Spherical triangle

Cosines formula:

$$\cos a = \cos b \cos c + \sin b \sin c \cos A$$

$$\cos b = \cos a \cos c + \sin a \sin c \cos B$$

$$\cos c = \cos a \cos b + \sin a \sin b \cos C$$

Five-element formulas of a spherical triangle:

$$\sin a \cos B = \sin a \cos b - \sin b \cos c \cos A$$

$$\sin b \cos C = \sin a \cos c - \sin a \cos a \cos B$$

$$\sin a \cos A = \sin b \cos a - \sin a \cos b \cos C$$

The above formulas address many issues related to celestial bodies. The transition from one of the celestial coordinates to another is carried out using a paralactic triangle.

It is said that a paralactic triangle is a spherical triangle whose ends lie in zenith, at the pole of the universe and at the Illuminator. Applying the formulas of the spherical triangle to the paralactic triangle, it is possible to derive the following coordinate substitution formulas for a given geographical latitude φ .

The transition from horizontal coordinates (a, h or z) to the first Equatorial coordinates (t, δ) is made using the following formulas.

$$\sin \delta = \cos z \sin \varphi - \sin z \cos \varphi \cos A$$

$$\cos \delta \cos t = \cos \varphi \cos z + \sin \varphi \sin z \cos A$$

$$\text{or } \sin t \cos \delta = \sin A \sin z$$

2) While the transition from Equatorial coordinates (t, δ) to horizontal coordinates (a, h or z) is performed using formulas:

$$\cos z = \sin \delta \sin \varphi + \cos \delta \cos \varphi \cos t$$

$$-\sin z \cos A = \cos \varphi \sin \delta - \sin \varphi \cos \delta \cos t$$

$$\text{or, } \sin t \cos \delta = \sin A \sin z$$

Note: to find the correct output (α) of the luminaire from the equatorial coordinates, the formula $T_y = \alpha + t$ is used, which represents the connection between the spring equinox point (Y) and the correct output α of that luminaire and the clockwise T. Where $tY = s$ is referred to as Star Time. And the height of the luminaire is found from the equality $h + z = 90^\circ$, that is

$$h = 90^\circ - z.$$

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